

“Geomechanical Criteria for Improving the Efficacy of the Injectors for Water Injection in Deepwater Turbidites: Example from the Gulf of Mexico”

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ABSTRACT

The deepwater turbidite fields of Mars and Ursa in the Gulf of Mexico are highly productive due to Pleistocene to Miocene sands, but they operate with insufficient aquifer drive. Maintaining reservoir pressure above the bubble point is imperative for sustaining high production and enhancing sweep efficiency. Efforts to implement water flooding for this purpose have faced challenges due to injectivity loss in the existing injector wells. A geomechanical analysis of the causes of injection loss, along with proposed solutions, has been suggested to restore injectivity in current injectors and determine the appropriate drilling mode for effective injection in new injector wells. The earth stress state has also been analyzed to recommend the well trajectory, considering future hydraulic fracturing needs and possible sand ingress.

Keywords: Turbidites, Mars-Ursa, Geomechanics, Pressure maintenance, Water injectors, Permeability anisotropy, USRD, Hydraulic Fracturing, Perforation, and Sand production.

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INTRODUCTION

The Mars and Ursa fields in the Deepwater Gulf of Mexico (GOM) are prolific producers, with reservoirs ranging from Miocene to Pleistocene turbidites at a water depth of 3,000 ft^{I&II} (Figure 1). Production at the Mars field began in 1996 and reached its peak in June 2000. Due to limited primary recovery caused by inadequate aquifer support and an overpressured, highly compacting reservoir, this field is a strong candidate for secondary recovery. The waterflooding efforts aim to slow pressure decline, prevent the M1/M2 and E sands from dropping below their bubble point, and reduce certain compaction risks linked to well completions in the compressible formations^{III}.

The northern Greater Mars-Ursa intraslope basin in the Gulf of Mexico exhibits high-resolution sediment cycles from the late Miocene to the early Pliocene, occurring roughly every 0.5 million years (Figure 2). These cycles include deep-water fan lobes and channelized systems^{IV}. The

Cite This Paper: PRATAP V NAIR (2025). “Geomechanical Criteria for Improving the Efficacy of the Injectors for Water Injection in Deepwater Turbidites: Example from the Gulf of Mexico”. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ENGINEERING AND DEVELOPMENT (IJETED)* ISSN 2249-6149, vol. 15, no. 4, 2025, pp. 96-107. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15977991>

sediments from this period can be categorized by their seismic features, with high-amplitude packages indicating sand-rich areas, while lower-amplitude packages suggest finer sediments, as noted by Sanabria et al., 2003^V(Figure 3). A typical deep reservoir stratigraphy, based on Gamma ray (GR) and Resistivity log (RILD)^{VI}, is shown in Figure 2. The clay-rich nature of the Missouri River's mass transport complex is evident. The Marsa-Ursa Basin is a prolific oil-producing area with a complex history linked to its geological structure and hydrocarbon resources (Figure 3). Understanding this requires identifying zones of salt movement and the concept of a protected trap.

Figure 1 Oil Fields in Greater Mars-Ursa Basin(modified after^{I,II})

Figure 2 : Typical GR-Resistivity log of Mars field^{VI}

Figure 3: Trapping mechanisms in the Oil Fields in Greater Mars-Ursa Basin^{VII}

Problem Definition

The primary concern is the loss of injectivity in the current water injectors, resulting in their premature abandonment and failure to achieve their intended objectives. The causes of this issue and whether practical, workable solutions exist to revive the injector wells have been examined. These injectors are likely situated at optimal geological positions in the fields to enhance production through voidage compensation and maximize recovery. There is a plan to drill additional injectors in the future. However, the risk of encountering severe depletion-related problems that could impede achieving the objectives seems high at this stage.

Need for pressure maintenance

Mature fields make up a large part of the world's oil and gas reserves production. Throughout a field's lifespan, different reservoir zones may be developed, necessitating careful planning and continuous monitoring. Production wells are often supported by waterflood injection strategies across one or more zones, depending on the pressure and productivity of those zones. The development plan for the field relies on accurate downhole flow profiles and reservoir depletion characteristics. Notably, the reservoir exhibits favourable features, including high vertical and horizontal permeability, structural relief, and good connectivity.

Turbidite Reservoir Failure Mechanisms

The mechanisms that could cause the loss of injectivity in the injectors of Mars and Ursa Fields in deepwater GOM have been described based on past and current performance of water injectors in unconsolidated turbidite reservoirs. It is observed that twice as many injectors have been abandoned compared to those wells that inject water at inadequate rates or operate at sustained high rates.

Four mechanisms clearly explain the geomechanical causes of failures and poor water injection performance through these wells (Figure 4). These mechanisms assume that failure occurs near the injection wellbore and involve the geology of the inter-injector-producer areas. In summary, the mechanisms involved;

- (a) Mechanism #1: Loss of Sand Control and Influx of Formation Solids into the Well.
- (b) Mechanism #2: Plugging of Near-Wellbore Region by Components of the Injectant.
- (c) Mechanism #3: Degradation of the Reservoir Rock Properties as a Result of Mobilization of Formation Solids.
- (d) Mechanism #4: Widespread Shear Failure in the Rock around the Wellbore.

Figure 4: Possible impairment mechanisms as a function of distance from the injector

Unconsolidated turbidite reservoirs have low resistance to shear stress (stress-sensitive) and are highly susceptible to formation damage caused by well sanding. This sand 'liquefaction' occurs earlier in the perforated sections with higher water saturation. Geological variations, such as increased clay content, lower cohesion, a reduced frictional angle, and decreased permeability, can lead to a tendency for shear failure near the wellbore. In other words, these reservoirs tend to have a higher clay fraction. The increased clay content and lack of consolidation significantly promotes shear failure in rocks near the wellbore under elevated injection pressure. Additionally, a fining-upward sedimentary sequence may contribute, as fines migrate beyond a certain threshold and gradually wash out the perforation tunnel, eventually causing it to collapse when the injection pressure exceeds the sand's shear resistance.

The four mechanisms proposed could occur simultaneously and may lead to complete wellbore damage and loss of injectivity. This results in the formation of a shear failure zone with reduced permeability. I believe this will be confined to the high-clay and high-water-saturation sections of

the perforated intervals. These factors make the turbidite sands highly sensitive to high injection rates and pressures, which can cause rapid erosion near the perforation tunnel walls, subjecting them to shear stresses. Higher injection pressures can cause these zones to spall into the wellbore, blocking the fluid flow path and reducing injectivity to zero. Shear failure also relates to directional permeability or permeability anisotropy. The orientation of the perforation tunnel is also important. Since the sands are unconsolidated, their cohesive resistance is low, and high injection pressures generate shear stresses on the tunnel walls. Heterogeneities and anisotropies, such as horizontal permeability contrasts, play significant roles. The vertical injectors and the azimuth of the directional properties also influence the injection profile.

Some basic causes for failure would be:

- (1) Effects of pressure reduction and fluid movement contribute to formation breakdown due to viscous and inertial forces, which depend on the fluid and can potentially exceed tensile strength.
- (2) Pressure depletion increases grain-to-grain forces, which can potentially exceed the compressive strength and lead to failure.
- (3) Chemical attack, inertial, and viscous forces vary depending on fluid composition.

Proposed Solutions

The approach to resolve issues related to the loss of injectivity will be addressed separately for existing injectors and planned injectors. The revival plan for injectors in their current condition is also considered. Reviving existing injectors is particularly important because they may have been optimally located based on reservoir geology. Understanding the orientation of horizontal stresses is not only crucial for well planning but also for well completion, forming an essential basis for solutions^{VIII}(Figure 5). Injectors will require sand control measures, such as the installation of sand screens.

Figure 5: Envisaged Injection pattern around a horizontal injector oriented in the direction of minimum horizontal stress^{VIII}

Existing Injectors

The primary goal is to revive the abandoned injectors. Wellbores that failed early can be cleaned with emulsion breakers and defoamers as appropriate. Once injectivity is restored, injection pressure must be managed carefully to avoid large pressure differentials that could cause sanding again, as explained earlier. However, subsequent issues may likely recur.

If this does not work, the perforations can be sealed off. The perforation intervals can be re-evaluated based on petrophysical criteria, such as water saturation, caliper, and clay content, to provide valuable insights. Oriented reperforation by aligning the perforations parallel to the direction of the maximum horizontal stress is preferred to ensure a stable perforation tunnel, with a perforation shot density not exceeding eight shots per foot.

In unconsolidated sand reservoirs, the onset of sanding occurs in the direction of the minimum horizontal stress, necessitating that perforations be executed in the direction of the maximum horizontal stress (oriented perforation) to mitigate sand production or to defer sanding^{IX}. Ideally, a detailed analysis of the perforated intervals should be conducted, focusing on log responses (resistivity, water saturation, caliper), perforation density and direction, as well as directional properties. It is also wise to choose the coarser sections of the reservoir for re-perforation. Insights can be gained from the caliper log and water saturation calculations, as higher water saturation usually indicates weaker zones. In the Gulf of Mexico, the maximum horizontal stress direction might align with the N15-30W axis. Monitoring injection pressure carefully is essential to avoid large pressure differentials, which can be controlled by using managed injection volumes.

There is no evidence of deep formation damage (Figure 4). It also suggests that the extent of the damage zone extends about ten feet from the wellbore. The assumption here is that the original horizontal-to-vertical permeability anisotropy remains intact away from the damaged area. The higher vertical permeability makes horizontal drain hole drilling a suitable option. However, understanding the permeability contrast in the horizontal plane will determine the azimuth of the drain hole. A drain hole aligned with the maximum horizontal stress will be a more effective injector than one randomly placed, as it will inject water in the direction of maximum permeability (Figure 6). The directions of maximum and minimum horizontal stresses (S_H and S_h) usually align with the maximum and minimum permeability directions. This helps avoid issues related to sand failure and shear stress. The occurrence of shear failure could serve as indirect evidence of stress anisotropy.

Reviving the injectors is possible if it is feasible to bypass the damaged area near the bore. This will require a thorough analysis of the reservoir features from well to well. If attempts do not yield positive results, horizontal drain holes can be installed in the reservoir to target the reservoir well before the shear failure zone, utilizing USRD technology^X and completing the well with, for example, a slotted pipe (Figure 6). USR drilling involves a buildup rate of 100°/100 feet to a maximum of 230°/100 feet or a radius of curvature between 25 and 57 feet. A lateral length of up to 600 feet has been achieved in other cases.

Figure 6: Possible sidetrack from vertical injector well with near wellbore damage^X

New Injectors

The importance of correctly orienting the horizontal well section in terms of stress is crucial for the success of the new injector. A horizontal injector may be drilled along the direction of minimum horizontal stress. Still, if it is intended to be hydraulically fractured, it should be drilled along the direction of maximum horizontal stress. Typically, hydraulic fracturing is not recommended for unconsolidated rocks due to a high risk of out-of-zone injection. However, in these fields with low permeability, a horizontal well aligned with the minimum horizontal stress tends to be the most stable in a normal faulting regime. Usually, these align with the direction of minimum horizontal permeability, so a well oriented along S_h can inject into a zone with higher horizontal permeability^{XI}. The stress concentration around the wellbore may cause the creation of longitudinal fractures in the near-wellbore zone, which reorient into transverse fractures beyond this region (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Fracture orientation in horizontal wells oriented in S_h and S_H directions^{XI}

Hydraulic Fracturing Strategy

The goal for the wellbore architecture is to intercept multiple hydrocarbon units separated by shale barriers, while maintaining a more horizontal orientation in zones with continuous high-net sands. Suppose the well azimuth is set to generate transverse fractures. In that case, these fractures will extend perpendicular from the well into the reservoir, expanding reservoir contact and enhancing hydrocarbon recovery compared to a vertical well^{XII} (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Well Architecture - Fracture orientation for vertical wellbores and horizontal wellbores with oblique perforations^{XII}

For hydraulic fracturing, it is preferable to orient the horizontal well in the SH direction. This alignment matches the maximum horizontal stress direction, causing all induced fractures to align along this path. Fracturing in other directions may unnecessarily increase tortuosity. Although experts may have different opinions about the effectiveness of hydraulic fracturing in horizontal wells aligned with S_h ^{XI} (refer to Figure 9), it is observed that fractures in horizontal wells aligned with S_h tend to be more tortuous, which could lead to out-of-zone injection at higher pressures (Figure 7). Therefore, it is concluded that horizontal wells oriented in the SH direction are the best choice for hydraulic fracturing based on the reasons given above.

Figure 9: Azimuth for horizontal drilling in various stress regimes^{XI}

Perforation Strategy

Reevaluating perforation intervals based on criteria such as water saturation, caliper, and clay content can offer valuable insights. In vertical wells, perforations can be shot in any direction but are typically oriented horizontally. Oriented reperforation, aligning the perforations parallel to the maximum horizontal stress, is preferred to ensure a stable perforation tunnel, usually with a perforation shot density not exceeding 8spf. In unconsolidated sand reservoirs, sand ingress tends to start in the direction of minimum horizontal stress; therefore, perforations should be performed in the direction of maximum horizontal stress (oriented perforation) to prevent or delay sand production^{XIII}. Figure 10 illustrates the fracture orientation for different trajectories aligned with various earth stresses^{XIV}. Petrophysical assessment is crucial regarding perforations on the low side along the gravity axis and the size of perforation entrance holes.

Figure 10: Schematic of Fracture orientation and wellbore trajectories^{XIV}.

Perforations located on the upper side of horizontal wells tend to exhibit greater stability and are less prone to failure or blockage due to debris. Perforations may be strategically aimed slightly off vertical to achieve optimal shot density and spacing, thereby enhancing productivity, decreasing pressure drop, and minimizing sand production^{XV}. Guidance can be obtained from the caliper log and water saturation calculations. High water saturation occurs near weak zones. The maximum horizontal stress direction in GOM may be along the axis of N15-30W. This is based on the World Stress Map^{XVI}(Figure 11). However, injection pressure must be controlled to prevent large pressure differentials, and this can be achieved through controlled injection volume.

Figure 11: Part of World Stress Map^{XVI}

Suggested Approach

The geomechanical approach to optimizing the pressure maintenance scheme, which ensures reservoir pressure stays above the bubble point for optimal recovery, has two main components.

- If attempts to revive the existing failed injectors through cleanup are unsuccessful, the damaged area can be bypassed by creating a drain hole in the desired direction using USRD technology.
- New injectors, preferably horizontal wells, should be drilled toward SH, anticipating future hydraulic fracturing and perforated in the SH direction for future sand control.

CONCLUSION

To enhance water injector performance in deepwater turbidite reservoirs, such as those in the Gulf of Mexico, it is crucial to understand the reservoir's geomechanical characteristics and behavior thoroughly. Incorporating geomechanical modeling, stress analysis, and wellbore integrity monitoring is vital for effective water injection. By integrating these components into the strategy, oil recovery can be significantly improved while minimizing the risks associated with deepwater injection.

The causes behind the loss of injectivity in current water flood injectors within Pleistocene-Miocene turbidite reservoirs of deepwater Gulf of Mexico fields, including Mars and Ursa, have been identified. Key findings highlight the importance of considering geomechanical factors to improve waterflood performance. The suggested solutions focus on two main strategies: refurbishing existing injectors through targeted cleanup and drilling new horizontal injectors aligned in SH direction, combined with the use of oriented perforations and a hydraulic fracturing approach.

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